

Using hybrid-true-seeds to improve potato crop production

Problem

Breeding and seed-multiplication can be slow processes in conventional potato breeding (see Figure 1.A). Due to complex genetics, difficulties in targeting specific sites and unpredictable breeding, there is a lack of genetic gain in potato yield. As conventional potato breeding relies on bulky seed tubers, which makes obtaining clean starting material difficult and practically inefficient, this adds another limitation.

Solution

Hybrid breeding (Figure 1.B) of diploid potato is a solution to breed faster and provide clean starting material. Simpler genetics allow for faster combination of beneficial traits through breeding. Specific desired traits, such as late blight resistance, can be introduced relatively quickly through natural crossing. Multiplication through true seeds allows for the bulk up of millions of disease-free seeds within two years.

Benefits

Hybrid-true-seeds bring many advantages compared to seed tubers as starting material (Figure 2). It is possible to stack multiple desired traits in one hybrid true seed. For example, Solynta developed late blight-resistant hybrids in two years' time, that were demonstrated to be resistant to late-blight in phytophthora-inoculated field trials (Su et al., 2019). True hybrid seeds are very small; 25 g of seeds is enough to fill a whole hectare, compared to 2500 kg seed tubers, enabling faster upscaling. True seeds can be stored for several years, while seed tubers need to be used in the next season. True seeds are disease free, so starting material is always clean. New hybrids can be brought to the market faster (2-4 years compared to >15 years). Fast introduction of resistant hybrids, which means less pesticides are required.

Applicability box

Theme

Crop hybrid-breeding

Agronomic conditions

True hybrid seeds are sown and raised in greenhouse conditions. Seedlings can be transplanted to the field 6-7 weeks after sowing. Transplant as soon as there is no risk of freezing anymore. Tubers can be harvested.

Application time

Beginning of growing season (Spring months)

Required time

The growing season (Spring to late-Summer/Autumn)

Period of impact

Actual crop

Equipment

Planting can be done by-hand, potato harvester

Best in

Potatoes

Figure 1.A) Conventional breeding. Two heterogeneous tetraploids are crossed. Due to genetic complexity, the outcome of the crossing is unpredictable. This leads to slow genetic progress, and it is impossible to stack desired traits.

Figure 1.B) Hybrid breeding. In hybrid breeding, we produce homozygous parent lines through several generations of self-pollination. As the genetics is less complex than in tetraploids, it is much easier to select for traits and to combine them. By crossing two inbred lines, we combine the best traits of the two parents. Because of the use of homozygous parent lines, the hybrid is predictable, and all offspring plants are identical. Source: Solynta 2018.

Practical recommendation

- When growing potatoes from true seeds, the season starts with sowing the seeds in trays and raising plantlets in a greenhouse, comparable with cabbage.
- The seedlings can be transplanted to the field with a planting machine. At the end of the growing season, the tubers can be harvested, they can be used as seed tubers by farmers in the next season.

Figure 2. (Left) Seeds planted in controlled environment greenhouse. Seedling can be then transplanted to the field (right). Solynta, 2021.

Further information
Video

- Click on the link for Solynta YouTube channel to find out more, including instructions and experiences with true seeds across Europe and beyond (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCLEkIBdnOmgvNA9FSwZvc_Q)
- 'How Late Blight resistant potato Hybrids were made' (English) <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t87EwoXTxZA>

Further readings

- Lindhout, P., et al. (2018). Hybrid Potato Breeding for Improved Varieties in Gefu Wang-Pruski (ed.). Achieving sustainable cultivation of potatoes Volume 1 Breeding, nutritional and sensory quality. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing Limited, Cambridge, UK. ISBN: 978 1 78676 100 2
- Su, Y., Viquez-Zamora, M., Uil, D., Sinnige, J., & Kruijt, H., Vossen, J., Lindhout, P. and Heusden, A. (2019). Introgression of Genes for Resistance against Phytophthora infestans in Diploid Potato. American Journal of Potato Research. 97. 10.1007/s12230-019-09741-8.

Weblinks

- Solynta (<https://www.solynta.com/>)

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Project website: www.solace-eu.net

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